

Bank Central Asia (BCA) Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding Bank Central Asia using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word "Bank Central Asia" within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Central Asia based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 7 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Sharia and Conventional Bank Central Asia (BCA), namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; (6) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding Bank Central Asia, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Central Asia; BCA Syariah; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

The banking world is currently experiencing rapid progress in the era of globalization. Apart from the conventional banks that have been known so far, currently banks are also starting to develop which operate in the sharia sector. Sharia banks are financial institutions that provide financing and other services related to sharia principles (Putra Pranoto & Diana, 2021). In general, Islamic banks are the same as conventional banks, but the difference only lies in the way they operate. Conventional banks apply an interest system, while Islamic banks implement a profit sharing system based on Islamic principles. PT Bank Central Asia Tbk is a financial institution that operates in the conventional and sharia sectors.

According to the official website of the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), Bank Central Asia (BCA) is one of the national private commercial banks, while Bank Central Asia Syariah is one of the Sharia Commercial Banks (BUS) (KNKS & Bappenas, 2020) . Bank Central Asia (BCA) and Bank Central Asia (BCA) Syariah are banking industries whose operational activities are to collect and distribute funds to individual and business customers. These two banks have their respective advantages. One of the advantages possessed by BCA is that it is the bank that provides the largest credit in Indonesia, offering a credit portfolio with a variety of products divided into consumer, SME, commercial and corporate categories (Pulumbara Jullie J.; Wangkar, Anneke, 2014). Meanwhile,

BCA has advantages Sharia is able to maintain a healthy level of financial performance from 2016-2020 through health analysis of Bank Central Asia Syariah utilizing the RGEC method (risk profile, good corporate governance, income and capital) to have a healthy financial condition (Rinaima, 2022). Based on research conducted on the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital), there are 9 studies studying BCA Syariah and 268 studies studying BCA Conventional. This research shows that the number of studies on BCA is less than research on conventional BCA. From the difference in the number of studies, it can be seen that there needs to be further study of research related to BCA Syariah.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Central Asia using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Bank Central Asia, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding Bank Central Asia, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

PT Bank Central Asia Tbk., also known as BCA, is one of the largest private banks in Indonesia. On February 21 1957, BCA was founded under the name Bank Central Asia NV which is an important part of the Salim Group. Currently, BCA is owned by the largest cigarette business group in the world (Syarif et al., 2018) . BCA is also the parent bank of BCA Syariah. BCA Syariah is the youngest bank which officially started operating on April 5 2010 (Putra Pranoto & Diana, 2021) . Previously, BCA Syariah was PT Bank Utama Internasional (UIB) which was acquired by PT Bank Central Asia Tbk. based on Acquisition Deed No. 72 on June 12 2009 (Rinaima, 2022).

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other

qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library studies. The research object is Bank Central Asia (BCA) Sharia and Conventional. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Bank Central Asia (BCA) originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Bank Central Asia " for the entire year (20 03 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on Library Research.

Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses research mapping related to Sharia and Conventional BCA using the VOSviewer bibliometric study method and Library Researchs. Based on searches on the Garuda website, scientific publications for 20 years, namely 2003 to 2022, there are 270 articles discussing Sharia and Conventional BCA.

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional

The results of searching scientific publications regarding Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional in the period from 2003 to 2022, show instability in the form of increases and decreases in article publications each year. The highest number of publications was in 2021 with 45 articles. The number of articles about Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional is 270 published articles, so the average number of scientific publications about Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional is 18 articles every year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2003	1	2013	10	2018	31
2009	1	2014	16	2019	24
2010	3	2015	18	2020	33
2011	1	2016	19	2021	45
2012	4	2017	31	2022	33
Total 270					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 2 shows that there are 34 institutions in the top 7 positions as affiliates/institutions with the highest number of publications. EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research is an affiliate/journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results on Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional, namely 13 articles.

Table 2. Institutions and journals that publish scientific publications regarding Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Amount Publication
EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research	13
FEB Student Scientific Journal	12
Journal of Business Administration	10
Journal of Scientific Accounting Studies, Faculty of Economics, UNTAN (KIAFE)	7
EKONOMIA, Student Online Journal (JOM) in the Field of Economics, Procuratio: Scientific Journal of Management.	4
Hasanuddin Journal of Applied Business and Entrepreneurship, Journal of Effective Economics, Journal of Economics, Tourism and Hospitality Management, Civil Engineering Student Journal.	3
IJHCM (International Journal of Human Capital Management), International Journal of Economics, Business	2

and Accounting Research (IJEBAR), J-MAS (Journal of Management and Science), JEBI (Indonesian Journal of Business Economics), AKUNESA Accounting Journal, Journal of Business Disruption, JURNAL ECONOMICS AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP, Economic and Management Journal, Exist Journal, Muhammadiyah Aceh Management Scientific Journal, Management, Economics and Accounting Scientific Journal, Batanghari Jambi University Scientific Journal, Management Update Journal, Tambusai Education Journal, Pilar Nusa Mandiri Journal, Journal of Economics and Accounting Publications (JUPEA), JATISI (Journal of Informatics Engineering and Information Systems), JWM (JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT INSIGHTS), CREATIVE: Scientific Journal of Management Study Program, Pamulang University, Course: Journal of Accounting, Entrepreneurship and Business, METIK JURNAL, Wacana Journal of Social and Humanity Studies, YUME: Journal of Management.

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows that the most productive researcher discussing Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional is M. Taufik Hidayat with a total of 4 publications.

Table 3. Productivity of researchers regarding Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional

Researcher	Number of Publications
M. Taufik Hidayat	4
Darwin Lie (Lecturer), Imhar (Panca Sakti University Bekasi)	3
Efendi Efendi (Lecturer), Mesra Lindawati (Mercu Buana University, Jakarta, Indonesia), Gatot Kusjono (Pamulang University), Sabri Nurdin (Samarinda State College of Engineering), Andi Wijaya (Lecturer), Herman Karamoy (Sam Ratulangi University Manado), Ming Narto Wijaya, Tommy Kuncara (Gunadarma University), Ria Agustina (Gunadarma University), Silvia Sari Sitompul (STIE Pelita Indonesia), Frederik G. Worang, Darmeinis (Panca Sakti University)	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Sharia and Conventional Bank Central Asia

Based on search results on the Garuda website, there are 270 research articles discussing Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional. Then, the articles were exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format and input and analyzed using VOSviewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Bank Central Asia Sharia and Conventional

Source: Processed data, VOS viewer software 1.6.18.

The results of the co-word map network visualization of research developments regarding Sharia and Conventional Asia Central Banks are grouped into 8 clusters and 196 topics as follows:

- Cluster 1. Red, consists of 39 topics, namely: according, amount, approach, Bank BCA, Bank Central Asia Tbk, Bank Rakyat Indonesia, calculation, case, cash, company, comparison, credit, debtor, fund, human resource, idle money, IFRS, impact, implementation, increase, investor, KPR, law, liquidity, management, money, mortgage, MVA, object, observation, principle, profit, PSAK, researcher, risk, role, salary, system, value.
- Cluster 2. Green, consisting of 37 topics, namely: addition, application, assurance, ATM, Bank Central Asia, Bank Mandiri, banking, BCA, BCA Bank, business continuity, consumer, convenience, corporate image, customer, customer satisfaction, customer service, ease, empathy, bank, function, intention, internet banking, mobile banking, product, quality, questionnaire, reliability, responsiveness, satisfaction, service, service quality, significant impact, system, teller, term, transaction, trust.
- Cluster 3. Dark blue, consisting of 31 topics, namely: analysis technique, aspect, assessment, bank, Bank Central Asia Syariah, Bank Indonesia, BCA Syariah, BOPO, capital, condition, development, earnings, financial performance, financial ratio, financial statement, good corporate governance, health, information, IPO, level, liquidity ratio, NPF, partial effect, profitability, profitability ratio, ratio, RGEC, RGEC method, risk profile, significant difference, soundness.
- Cluster 4. Yellow, consisting of 27 topics, namely: achievement, attention, Bank Central Asia Syariah Tbk branch, bank service quality,

change, classical assumption test, compensation, covid, employee, employee performance, employee performance, environment, incentive, influence, job satisfaction, employee performance, leadership, organization, organizational commitment, organizational culture, pandemic, performance, PT Bank Central Asia, significant influence, spirit, work discipline, work motivation.

- Cluster 5. Purple, consisting of 22 topics, namely: capital structure, determination, exchange rate, f test, firm value, inflation, interest rate, LMX, multiple linear regression, OCB, organizational citizenship, price, profit growth, program, PT BCA, PT BCA Syariah Tbk, significant effect, significant value, stock price, stock split, t test.
- Cluster 6. Light blue, consisting of 19 topics, namely: analysis, assets, capital adequacy ratio, car, corporate social responsibility, CSR, deposit ratio, EPS, equity, funding ratio, LDR, LFR, loan, non-performing loan, NPL, performing loan, return, ROA, ROE.
- Cluster 7. Orange color, consisting of 14 topics, namely: customer loyalty, customer retention, customer satisfaction, effect, explanatory research, job motivation, loyalty, marketing mix strategy, path analysis, quantitative approach, relationship marketing, role performance, role performance employees, self-efficacy.
- Cluster 8. Brown color, consisting of 7 topics, namely: branch, employee job satisfaction, experience, motivation, PT Bank Central Asia Tbk, relationship, significance effect.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Financial Performance of Conventional Bank Central Asia (BCA)

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 22 topics related to the financial performance of Bank Central Asia (BCA) Conventional, namely:

First, the influence of being acquired by foreign investors, the concept of Balanced Scorecard, Initial Public Offering /IPO, liquidity ratios, leverage, profitability, interest rates, inflation, Covid-19, Operational Costs to Operating Income/BOPO, Capital Adequacy Ratio/ CAR, Non Performing Loans/ NPLs, and ownership structure on financial performance.

Second, the influence of inflation, credit quality, credit risk, liquidity, and Corporate Social Responsibility /CSR, gap ratio, foreign exchange ratio, mobile banking, and Good Corporate Governance /GCG on the level of profitability.

Third, the influence of PSAK 50 and 55 on Allowance for Impairment Losses/CKPN.

Fourth, healthy financial performance using the RGEC (Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, Capital), IFRS (International Financial Reporting Standards), Islamicity Performance Index /IPI, and CAMEL approach.

Fifth, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR, Non Performing Loans / NPL, Return On Assets / ROA, Return On Equity / ROE, Net Interest Margin / NIM, Loan to Deposit Ratio / LDR, exchange rates, interest rates, inflation, Earnings Per Share/ EPS, stock split, inflation, currency exchange rate fluctuations, BI Rate, and transaction volume on share prices.

Sixth, the influence of PSAK No. 10 of 2012 on financial reports.

Seventh, the influence of Home Ownership Credit/KPR on Non-Performing Loans /NPL.

Eighth, forecasting stock returns using Self Exciting Threshold Autoregressive-Genetic Algorithm, K-Nearest Neighbors /KNN, and HOLT'S method.

Ninth, the influence of PSAK 60 on disclosure of financial asset information.

Tenth, the influence of RBBR financial ratios, exchange rates, inflation, and Cash Deposit Machines on company profit growth.

Eleventh, investment risk using the Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity /GARCH approach.

Twelfth, managing idle money.

Thirteenth, the level of credit risk and liquidity risk.

Fourteenth, the influence of information technology and internal control on the quality of management accounting information systems.

Fifteenth, fixed asset logistics data collection information system.

Sixteenth, the influence of capital structure and external factors on company value.

Seventeenth, the influence of Non Performing Loans / NPL, Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR, Loan to Deposit Ratio / LDR on Return On Equity / ROE.

Eighteenth, the influence of Capital Adequacy Ratio /CAR, Loans Deposit Ratio /LDR, Return On Assets /ROA on net profit.

Nineteenth, the influence of Non Performing Loans / NPL, Net Interest Margin / NIM, Operational Costs on Operating Income / BOPO, and Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR on Return On Assets / ROA.

Twentieth, the influence of Earning Assets on net interest income.

Twenty-first, cash receipt procedures.

Twenty-second, the effect of cash turnover on liquidity.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Conventional Bank Central Asia (BCA) Employee Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 51 topics related to Bank Central Asia (BCA) employee performance Conventional, namely: (1) Back office based on information technology; (2) Work load; (3) Organizational culture; (4) Core Competencies; (5) Customer relationship management using the Zachman Framework; (6) Work discipline; (7) Digital banking; (8) Employer branding; (9) Employee value; (10) Employee Stock Ownership Program / ESOP; (11) Emotional; (12) Business ethics; (13) Good Corporate Governance /GCG; (14) Employment relations; (15) Integrity; (16) Incentives; (17) Individual characteristics; (18) Transformational leadership; (19) Job satisfaction; (20) Organizational commitment; (21) Emotional and intellectual intelligence; (22) Horizontal communication; (23) Employee involvement; (24) Compensation; (25) Organizational justice; (26) Teamwork; (27) Management information system security; (28) Leader Member Exchange /LMX; (29) Work environment; (30) Loyalty; (31) Years of service; (32) Work motivation; (33) Individual morality; (34) Intention; (35) Organizational Citizenship Behavior /OCB; (36) Outsourcing; (37) Work experience; (38) Job performance assessment; (39) Training; (40) Career development using e-learning; (41) Profile matching; (42) Rewards; (43) Job rotation; (44) Internal control system; (45) Spiritual; (46) Job stress; (47) Self-efficacy; (48) Attendance information system; (49) Social responsibility; (50) Work-life balance; and (51) Work from home /WFH.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Conventional Bank Central Asia (BCA) Customer Behavior

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 46 topics related to Bank Central Asia (BCA) customer behavior Conventional, namely: (1) Automatic Teller Machine /ATM (tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy); (2) Automated Teller Machines/ATMs; (3) Term stage insurance; (4) Services marketing mix; (5) Brand image; (6) Customer Engagement; (7) Customer service; (8) Debit cards; (9) Website design; (10) Digital marketing; (11) Product differentiation; (12) E-Service Quality; (13) E-Banking; (14) Empathy; (15) Facilities; (16) Innovative; (17) Internal marketing; (18) Internet banking; (19) Security; (20) Need; (21) Debit card; (22) Responsiveness; (23) Friendliness; (24) Reliability; (25) Self-confidence; (26) Communication; (27) Compensation; (28) Usefulness; (29) Convenience; (30) Quality of service; (31) Brand awareness; (32) Customer satisfaction; (33) Customer Service Officer Performance; (34) Mobile banking (completeness of features and navigation design); (35) Creating an online account; (36) Relationship marketing; (37) Understanding; (38) Front liner service; (39) Order Chatbot for online small money exchange; (40) Reliability; (41) Responsiveness; (42) Queuing system; (43) Promotion strategy with SWOT; (44) Social responsibility; (45) Tangibility; and (46) Service time.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Conventional Bank Central Asia (BCA) Financing/Credit Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 10 research topics related to Bank Central Asia (BCA) financing products Conventional, namely:

First, the influence of financing on credit risk.

Second, the influence of the internal control system and Good Corporate Governance /GCG on procedures for granting working capital credit.

Third, legal protection of shareholders.

Fourth, the influence of Non-Performing Loans / NPL, Capital Adequacy Ratio / CAR, Third Party Funds / DPK, credit interest rates, Minimum Statutory Reserves / GWM on credit distribution.

Fifth, the influence of competitive fixed and cap interest rates on Home Ownership Credit/KPR financing.

Sixth, resolving bad/problematic credit.

Seventh, disclosure of fraud in credit financing using the implementation of Good Corporate Governance /GCG and organizational culture.

Eighth, guarantee/collateral in financing.

Ninth, forecasting commercial credit financial distress using the Altman Z-Score.

Tenth, the effect of controlling receivables on minimizing bad debts.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Conventional Bank Central Asia (BCA) Savings Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 1 research topic related to Bank Central Asia (BCA) savings/deposit products Conventional, namely: the influence of Gross Domestic Product/GDP and deposit interest rates on the amount of term savings.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues in Conventional Central Asia (BCA) Banks

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 19 research topics related to issues at Bank Central Asia (BCA), namely:
First, measuring the level of information technology risk exposure using the FMEA method.

Second, implementing Business Continuity.

Third, disclosure of Corporate Social Responsibility / CSR in the Sustainability Report based on the Global Reporting Initiative G4.

Fourth, integration of the Servqual method, quality function deployment /QFD, and Kaizen to improve the quality of operational services.

Fifth, the information system uses the IT Balanced Scorecard.

Sixth, the influence of manual and electronic clearing systems on work productivity.

Seventh, implementation of bank guarantees.

Eighth, implementing a whistleblowing system against internal fraud.

Ninth, the influence of supply chain efficiency on cash management performance.

Tenth, identify ATM fraud by comparing seven algorithms.

Eleventh, implementation of good corporate governance.

Twelfth, application of prototyping methodology in designing a referral recording information system.

Thirteenth, estimate company risk using Value At Risk with the ARIMAX-GARCHX approach.

Sixteenth, company industrial relations in determining minimum wages for workers.

Seventeenth, acquisition of Bank Royal Indonesia by Bank Central Asia.

Eighteenth, the influence of financial technology/ fintech on banking strategy.

Nineteenth, the influence of Corporate Social Responsibility /CSR on community development programs.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Central Asia (BCA) Sharia

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 8 research topics related to Bank Central Asia (BCA) Sharia, namely:

First, the company's health level using the CAELS, CAMEL, and RGEC (Risk Profile, Good Corporate Governance, Earnings, Capital) ratio calculation method.

Second, comparison of Home Ownership Credit/KPR financing at BCA Syariah and Conventional.

Third, the influence of exchange rates and inflation on profit growth.

Fourth, the influence of Non Performing Financing / NPF, Operational Costs on Operational Income / BOPO, Financing to Deposit Ratio / FDR, Mudharabah financing, Musyarakah financing on Return On Assets / ROA.

Fifth, comparison of the financial performance of BCA Syariah and Conventional.

Sixth, the influence of overhead costs, risk costs, Murabahah financing volume, and liquidity position on Murabahah margin income.

Seventh, the influence of financial distress on the company's health level.

Eighth, measuring the Islamicity Performance Index / IPI on financial performance.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 7 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Bank Central Asia (BCA) Sharia and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Customer behavior; (4) Financing/credit products; (5) Savings/deposit products; (6) Other issues.

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